

MANAGEMENT OF DISTRIBUTION CHANNELS IN MARKETING AND THE EFFECTS OF INTERMEDIARIES ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

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Abstract

The majority of business and marketing managers do not give due importance to the distribution function of the business. It is often viewed as a second-order function that must work in harmony with other functions. When the studies carried out to date are examined, it is seen that the studies have intensified in certain periods.

After production took on a mass character, a conflict of space, time, and property benefits emerged between the production and consumption processes. Distribution channels and intermediaries have been established to resolve these disputes and deliver most of the production that cannot be consumed on-site to the end users. Distribution channels are an indispensable tool for both the country's economy and the business economy, and their effectiveness leads to an increase in countries' gross national product.

The transportation of a good or service from its first producer to the end user and the routes it follows during transportation are defined as distribution channels and distribution channel systems. For this system to operate, several intermediaries are required. In distribution channels, these intermediaries can be broadly classified as wholesalers, retailers, agents, manufacturers, and consumers.

In today's world where customer satisfaction has gained importance, businesses must offer the products and services requested by the customer at the right place, at the right time, and at the right price. At this point, the importance of distribution channels that play an active role in delivering products and services to customers emerges.

Keywords: *Distribution Channel, Channels in Marketing, Customer Satisfaction*

Introduction

The distribution channel is one of the most critical elements of a marketing system. While the intermediaries in the channel earn profits by delivering the products of the producers to the consumers, they also ensure that the products that the consumers need are delivered to the consumers easily, quickly, and in the desired way.

Manufacturers use a significant portion of their resources for production; focus their attention in this area. They make significant use of intermediaries in bringing the produced products to the consumers. All kinds of promotional efforts made by producers make the job of intermediaries easier. Intermediaries also support the producing enterprise with all kinds of promotional activities. Dealers' personal sales efforts, public relations activities, advertisements, and sales promotion efforts are all effective for the manufacturer as well as for the dealer.

One of the objectives of the producer enterprise is to prevent a possible conflict that would negatively affect the cooperation between the intermediary companies in the distribution channel and the producers and to provide the necessary leadership understanding to shift the balance of power in the distribution channel to the side of the producer. The leadership of the manufacturing company plays a decisive role in motivating intermediaries in the distribution channel and improving the efficiency of distribution. Distribution channel leadership and motivation provide a basis for creating strong cooperation and competitive advantage in the distribution channel (Özdemir, 2005:116).

Distribution Channel Concept

In marketing, distribution channels are the process that a product or service follows from its producer to the consumer. In other words, it is a system formed by institutions and organizations that are in contact with each other and work for this purpose, delivering goods of exchange value from the place where they are produced to the place where they are consumed. Distribution channels provide very important contributions for companies, namely manufacturers. Through distribution channels, companies can obtain information about the market environment and consumer groups and also enable them to promote and carry out promotional activities for the products offered. Thanks to distribution channels, companies can establish relationships with buyers and identify the products and services that consumers need. In addition, among the benefits that distribution channels provide to the manufacturer; transferring ownership by making purchases and sales, establishing and developing relationships with physical distribution companies that carry out orders, storage, and transportation, etc. There are. Distribution channels are in a relationship with each other as well as with the manufacturer (Tunc, 2015:37).

Direct distribution is, used in the sense that the manufacturer has created its own distribution channels. This is a difficult and costly work. This falls within the scope of direct distribution and can be done depending on criteria such as the production region and the consumption region being close to each other, the products being standardized, and supply and demand being in a certain balance. However, compared to companies that follow other distribution channels, this method remains more professional. In indirect distribution channels,

each intermediary is after his own profit and this distribution system is not a system that the producer can control. Every intermediary company can cooperate with whomever it wants. This situation depends entirely on the intermediary's relations of interest among each other. In integrated distribution channels, an intermediary is formed when he/she wishes to act together with another distribution intermediary in the same distribution channel. The important point here is that one firm among integrated intermediaries influences the others. An agent influences the management and action of others (Muratoglu, 2012: 30).

A company creates a vertically integrated distribution channel by adding the work within its scope to its own work during the production phase or during its distribution. If the company incorporates other distribution companies working in this sense, it already creates a direct distribution channel. Retailers eliminate manufacturers and intermediary distribution companies. Some of them are even starting to carry out one stage of production in-house. Here too, backward vertical integration can be mentioned. This situation can be transformed into forward vertical integration by the manufacturer, if the manufacturer disables the distribution channels, carries out all the work itself, and begins to supervise the intermediaries through contracts. The new structure formed as a result of the merger of two intermediary firms, either for a certain period or continuously, is horizontal integration. Multi-channel marketing system can also be done by using different distribution channels that occur when manufacturers want to enter different markets (Kir, 2013:19).

Distribution Channel Types

Distribution channels define the path that goods and services take from the manufacturer to the end consumer. These channels play a crucial role in getting products into the hands of customers. Essentially, they are the routes through which products move from production to consumption. Distribution channels are classified in various ways. A traditionally common distinction is based on the nature of the relationships between channel members and can be classified as distribution depending on whether the relationship in question is direct or indirect.

Direct Distribution: Direct distribution is a model that companies sell products directly to customers without any intermediaries. For instance, a brand might operate its own stores or sell online through its website. It is the distribution system carried out by the manufacturer with its own sales organization. In other words, it is the situation where the manufacturer sells the product directly to the consumer (final or industrial) through various channels. In other words, the buying and selling process is done through the distribution channel, with the producer at one end and the consumer at the other. In direct distribution, the manufacturer addresses the consumer directly and carries out the necessary marketing functions. However, in order for direct distribution to occur, all or some of the following conditions must be met and all or some of them must be present; (Li at al., 2024: 588, Cantini at al., 2024: 3023, Kim at al., 2024: 3052).

Short distance between production and consumption areas.

Production and consumption tempos are the same or similar.

The number of consumers is small or consumers are concentrated in certain centers.

Products are sufficiently standardized.

From an organizational perspective, direct distribution has centralized and decentralized types. In central direct distribution; Goods can be delivered to the consumer from factory warehouses or a small number of regional warehouses. This type has benefits in terms of rationality because the functions are gathered at one point. In decentralized direct distribution, management, coordination and control difficulties are encountered. In this type of distribution, which is mostly applied to convenience goods and preferred goods, legal, administrative and economically dependent bodies are used (Paksoy, 2005, Dursun and Gursev, 2016). Some advantages of direct distribution can be listed as follows (Grönroos, 1997, Heliste, 2019, Obadia and Vida, 2024, Ozmen at al., 2013);

- Makes the necessary changes and corrections in the marketing mix elements.

- The producer generally has wide freedom of action.

- Sales activities can be controlled effectively.

- When an extraordinary sales effort or technical service is required, the producer has the opportunity to better monitor changes in the market by establishing a close relationship with the producer and consumer; It can know whether it can be achieved in production and with its own sales organization according to changes in demand.

Indirect distribution: It is the situation where the buying and selling relationship between the producer and the consumer is provided by commercial organizations with legal and economic independence. In indirect distribution channels, customers may have different attitudes towards distributors and brands. Here, buyers' loyalty to brands will come to the fore. However, in this context, brand loyalty is still a problem in indirect distribution channels (Eggert at al., 2012). Many factors such as consumer preferences, geographical conditions, and costs may be effective in determining indirect distribution channels. (Alden, 1982, Takata, 2019,). Some indirect distribution channel methods can be expressed as follows; Retailers and Wholesalers, Agents and Brokers, Franchises, Online Marketplaces, Distributors and Dealers, Value-Added Resellers (VARs) and Industrial Distributors (Rao, 1999, Datta and Sanyal, 2016, Dent and White, 2018, Karaca-Mandic at al., 2018, Lee at al., 2021, Yang nad the others, 2024, Baisya, 2024, Li, 2024, Shi at al., 2024).

Retailers and Wholesalers: Retail outlets (physical or online) act as intermediaries, increasing a brand's visibility and reaching diverse locations. Wholesalers, on the other hand, purchase products in bulk from manufacturers and distribute them to retailers. In general, the majority of products distributed in the domestic market are put on the market by wholesalers. Nowadays, they have kept up with the times in wholesale sales and continue their sales through the

electronic market. This situation is also observed in retail distributors. Traditional retailers need to keep up with modern methods in order to survive.

Agents and Brokers: These intermediaries facilitate product movement. Agents represent manufacturers and negotiate deals with distributors, while brokers connect buyers and sellers without taking ownership of the products. The role of brokers and agents is particularly important for smaller companies that generally do not have the expertise and human resources departments to evaluate the product. Research shows that small companies generally procure supplies from brokers and agencies.

Franchises: Franchisees operate under a brand's established system, benefiting from its reputation and support. In franchising, two companies establish a relationship based on a licensing agreement. In this relationship, the franchisee obtains the right to sell its goods or services under its own brand, with the support of business resources, in exchange for entry fees and royalty payments from the franchisor. Thanks to these agreements, the parties mutually benefit. In franchise agreements, franchisees can harm the franchisor if they do not monitor their margins while sabotaging the franchise brand. Therefore, understanding the nature of franchise relationships and managing relationships effectively is key to a successful and sustainable franchise system.

Online Marketplaces: Recently, online marketplace sales have become more popular than other sales. The factor that caused this stop is the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak that occurred in 2019-2021. These applications also include classical retail or wholesale sellers in their systems. Examples of such application platforms can be given as follows. E-commerce platforms like Amazon, eBay, and Alibaba serve as distribution channels, connecting sellers with global consumers.

Distributors and Dealers: Distributors buy products from manufacturers and sell them to retailers or end consumers. Dealers often specialize in specific product categories.

Value-Added Resellers (VARs): VARs enhance products by adding value (e.g., customization, installation, support) before selling them to customers. Value-added services provided by a channel can increase the perceived value of products sold through that channel. From a channel services perspective, the service quality levels offered by two different suppliers often differ. In practice, an online retailer can offer value-added services to its consumers, such as fast logistics and safe return guarantees, to enhance their shopping experience. With such an evaluation, it is assumed that consumers' perception of service quality regarding the resale channel is higher than that offered by the marketplace channel. Distribution channels created for value-added sales generally increase the value of products to consumers, and product prices are sold at higher prices than their counterparts.

Industrial Distributors: These channels cater to business-to-business (B2B) sales, supplying industrial products to other businesses. The role and nature of business-to-business (B2B) sales have evolved since

the end of the 20th century, mostly due to technological, organizational and social changes. Today, this distribution channel is developing within the framework of the conditions.

The Place and Importance of the Distribution Channel in Marketing

The system of distribution channels is, first of all, the area where the business encounters consumers and competing businesses. In a sense, the business is showcased in the industry. Distribution policies will be of vital importance in an area where many activities and expenses of businesses will be evaluated. There is definitely interdependence and mutual interaction between departments within the internal structures of the businesses within the system. It will affect distribution policies, marketing activities and decisions, as well as the decisions and business strategies of other departments. Likewise, business objectives, marketing decisions and strategies will influence distribution policies. In reality, these strategies will determine distribution policies. However, this may not always be possible. Physical, financial, sectoral, legal, social, political, etc. In cases arising from factors, the business may have to comply with distribution channel decisions. The important thing here is to make optimal decisions that will achieve the goals of the business and to implement them effectively and efficiently. (Unusan, 1997: 85).

When distribution channels are considered as a member of the marketing system, they emerge as an element that must be managed correctly and well. This issue is directly reflected in customer satisfaction. If these situations are examined in general, it can be said that the most important one is the conflict in distribution channels.

Manufacturers, trying to effectively meet the demands and needs of consumers, benefit from different distribution channel members in delivering products to consumers. In order for manufacturers to perform their distribution function effectively, it is inevitable for them to benefit from these channel members. However, for the channel to be successful, good communication must be ensured between channel members. Otherwise, lack of communication between members may lead to deterioration of motivation, conflicts, and therefore decreased performance and decreased productivity. Such a distribution channel will be quite insufficient in the sale and distribution of products. This situation may cause conflict in the distribution channel. Conflict in the distribution channel has various consequences. While one of these may cause channel members to move away from the channel, recent studies have revealed that the conflict that occurs in distribution channels increases the solidarity in the channel. The first of these solidarities is the unification of the canal system. Channel members may decide that no other alternative relationship will be as effective in achieving their objectives as the current channel system. In this context, the second situation is when a change occurs in the system. If conflict accelerates a change in the system, which in turn improves performance, conflict can be considered positive. If one wants to survive in an intensely competitive environment, one should try to minimize the possibilities of conflict and try to create a

more functional distribution channel by managing the conflict effectively, thereby increasing the quality of service offered to customers (Gures, 2014: 234).

It is also extremely important to motivate members in distribution channels. It can be expressed that the motivation of the members is directly proportional to the accurate and timely supply of customer demands. While the realization of production is a great success in itself, delivering these products and services to the consumer on time and correctly is another success. It is a basic condition for the manufacturer to correctly determine the factors that determine the motivation of the dealers in the distribution channel and fulfill them for the system to run smoothly. In this regard, monetary rewards can be motivating, as well as non-monetary rewards (non-business relations, producer company representative, participation in decisions and consultation, loyalty to contracts with dealers, corporate services, professional activities of the manufacturer company, loyalty programs for dealers, training meetings, database support, etc.) will help with motivation (Özdemir, 2005: 121).

Manufacturers also need to monitor their distribution channels' relationships with customers. The sensitivity of consumers when choosing the product should also be taken into consideration by distribution channel members. Perceptions of consumers about products should be investigated and action should be taken to eliminate the resulting negative perceptions. In order to maintain and increase positive perceptions, it is necessary to be persistent (Oz, 2008: 432).

Conclusion

Manufacturers, trying to effectively meet the demands and needs of consumers, benefit from different distribution channel members in delivering products to consumers. In order for manufacturers to perform their distribution function effectively, it is inevitable for them to benefit from these channel members. However, for the channel to be successful, good communication must be ensured between channel members. Otherwise, lack of communication between members may lead to deterioration of motivation, conflicts, and therefore decreased performance and decreased productivity. Such a distribution channel will be quite insufficient in the sale and distribution of products. Therefore, in order to meet customers and create more value in the intense competition of channel members, where all members are interdependent and the performance of each depends on the power of the entire channel; They need mutual cooperation, understanding, commitment and teamwork.

The distribution channel is of great importance in delivering products to end users. Creating an effective distribution channel that will satisfy end users is important for both manufacturers and channel members. Therefore, attention should be paid to issues that may cause conflict in the channel. If one wants to survive in an intensely competitive environment, one should try to minimize the possibilities of conflict and try to create a more functional distribution channel by managing the conflict effectively, thereby increasing the quality of service offered to customers.

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